

EKSPLUATATION PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY OF FABRICS WITH INCREASED CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The quality and beauty of clothes are the main requirements of fashion. Today, the art of weaving our Uzbek national fabrics and the production of natural silk fiber, which is a necessary raw material for these fabrics, is developing rapidly. "Performance" refers to the properties of fabrics such as air permeability, elongation and friction, durability, permeability, color fastness, shape retention

Key words: Clothing, fabric, weaving, art, silk, bekasam.

The quality and appearance of clothes is the main requirement of fashion. Today, the art of weaving our Uzbek national fabrics, as well as the production of natural silk fiber, the raw material necessary for these fabrics, that is, the silk industry, is developing rapidly. In particular, the Decree of the first President I.Karimov dated March 30, 2010 "On further support for the development of folk arts and crafts" is an important factor for the development of this field and industries. The luster of our national fabrics, such as khonatlas, adras, bekasam, silk, and olacha, the eye-pleasing patterns, and the harmony of colors amaze everyone. We are all proud that in different countries of the world, modern style dresses are made from our beautiful fabrics and worn by people. Modernity and the spirit of nationalism are combined in the works of designers who create a collection of dresses using our natural silk fabrics. It is known that gauzes made of natural silk fibers and dresses made from them always attract attention with their beauty and lightness. These fabrics, which are becoming more popular year after year, are affected by modern clothing, and the fabric also affects the current clothing design through its operational and hygienic properties and quality indicators. If we take into account the exploitative properties of this national treasure - our fabrics - it is not appropriate to sew everyday clothes from them, which are intended for permanent wear. Before explaining why we came to such a stop, the operational characteristics of fabrics we want to pay attention to the problem. "Operational properties" refers to the qualities

of fabrics such as air permeability, effect on elongation and friction, durability, permeability, level of color rendering, shape retention in design. Having carefully studied these indicators, a dress project should be created. Having studied these qualities of our fabrics in the laboratory, we made sure that our silk fabrics are more comfortable for everyday wear. As an example, let's talk about some of our fabrics.

If we study the characteristics of durability and "reliability" of Margilon and this satin-type silk fabrics, the appearance and texture of this satin, the fact that this fabric does not pass air well is a good reason that the original color will not be preserved after the washing process. It causes certain inconveniences due to its penetration, that is, its narrowing after washing, which makes it difficult to sew a dress. Dresses made of satin or satin fabrics can retain some of their beauty and softness when they are mostly chemically cleaned. However, when washed in a washing machine, at home, if it is not treated with care, the fabric will not retain its appearance. Also, taking into account that it is difficult to pass air, if clothes are sewn from satin in a wider shape, such a dress is not very suitable for our girls and women. A tight-fitting dress made of satin will start to fray at the seams and around the seam after only a few wears. Therefore, it is appropriate to create and sew a project of clothes for events and holidays from satin, not everyday clothes that are worn all the time. Due to the fact that both silk fiber and cotton yarn fiber are used in the weaving of Adras, the air permeability of this fabric is relatively good. However, like satin, water has its effect on the elasticity of adras. When Adras is washed at home, its beauty decreases. Silk (excelsior) is composed of pure silk, it attracts attention with its very fine weave and softness. Dyeing this harir fabric in batik style and making various scarves is very popular nowadays. But this fabric has sewing problems. It is not right to make everyday clothes from silk. Of course, we do not want to spoil our national fabrics. After all, they are our national pride! However, if this beauty is not used in its proper place, i.e., if our fabrics are made only for festive and special days, we would say that it is appropriate. Our young designers are also mainly creating stage costumes. And this, in my opinion, leads to the limitation of styles in modern fashion. In order to avoid such a situation, it is necessary to pay attention to the bending process of the fibers used in weaving our fabrics. When we compare our old national fabrics with the ones being woven now, we can see that ancient satin-u bekasam has high quality indicators, and its color is preserved for a very long time. It is clear from this that at present, defects and perhaps some negligence are allowed in

the dyeing of silk fibers. In conclusion, we would like to say that if our weavers re-learn the secret of the previous natural dyes, the dyeing process and apply this method to the work process and create our national fabrics that are perfect in every aspect, our designers and tailors will be able to make everyday clothes from our fabrics. they were also boldly clapping hands.

Currently, the industry offers many different fabrics for clothing, each of which has its own characteristics, structure and properties. The properties of fabrics are determined by the properties of the fibers that are part of them. Today, sewing materials are produced on the basis of natural and chemical fibers. natural fabrics and fibers used for their production can be of plant, animal and mineral (asbestos) origin. The first group (vegetable tissues) includes those made of cotton fiber, flax stalk, hemp, jute, gorse and others. The group of natural animal tissues includes wool, as well as those made from sheep, goat, rabbit, vicuña, whiskers, wool, wool stalks. llamas, camels, alpacas. An independent group of fibers obtained from animals is natural silk fiber, which is a frozen secret from the special glands of silkworm caterpillars. chemical fiber is conventionally divided into 2 groups: man-made and synthetic. The first is obtained by special processing of mineral, vegetable or animal raw materials. Synthetic fiber is produced by synthesis of raw materials, which can be gas, oil, coal, etc. The most popular artificial fabrics are viscose (based on cellulose polymer solution), acetate (made by processing cellulose acetate solution), as well as copper-ammonia. Chemical synthetic fabrics are made from nylon, lavsan, chlorine and nitron fibers. Natural silk fabrics. Fabrics made of natural silk fibers look very attractive. Their main characteristics are hygiene, wear resistance and strength. Silk has a unique luster, the degree of which depends on the weaving method and the type of twisting of the warp and weft yarns. Silk fabric has a light and delicate texture. It is plastic, which allows it to be draped when sewing clothes, it is easy to wash and iron. Silk fabrics of the crepe group are resistant to wrinkling. Woolen fabrics. The raw materials for the production of woollens are wool and wool of animals (sheep, rabbit, llama, etc.). Wool fabrics are durable and hygienic. In addition, they retain heat well. Depending on the thickness of the threads, woolen fabrics are thin (crepe) and thick (drape, tweed). The fine wool fabric has a light silk sheen. Wool fabrics are plastic, soft, durable. The addition of other types of fibers to the raw materials makes them more elastic, resistant to felting (pilling) and wrinkling. Viscose fabrics. The chemical composition of viscose fabrics

is similar to linen and cotton. Like the latter, they have a hygienic and attractive appearance. In addition, they are easy to wash. Viscose staple is especially popular in the clothing industry, its main characteristics are light silk or matte shine, softness, plasticity, fluidity, as a result of which it can be draped. The main disadvantage of viscose fabric is relatively low strength (especially when wet). In addition, after washing, it shrinks significantly and wrinkles easily. The above negative properties of viscous gases are reduced by adding synthetic and other types of fibers to the raw materials in their production.

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